

Contributi/7

Habitus and Learning

Notes on Repetition, Body and Change

Igor Pelgreffi

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In this essay the modification of the *Habitus*, understood as the transformation of our behaviours (individual and collective) will be inquired, where transformation corresponds to new relationships between repetition and difference and it could have both an ethical and a political significance. *Habitus* and its embodiment participate in both the social sphere and the physical-corporeal sphere: it seems therefore necessary to start from the philosophical analysis of this social-corporeal *milieu*, in order to investigate the forms of dis-automation in our behaviour. After a reconnaissance of the philosophical foundations of *Habitus* in the Aristotelian notion of *hexis*, an analysis of Habits concept in Merleau-Ponty, Bourdieu and Mauss will be done. Social habits can change thanks to the *interaction* between pattern and corporeity, here in the sense of a pre-logical constitutive inter-corporeity capable to give shape and meaning to *Habitus* itself. From here, the topic of Second Nature and the transformative demand will be examined, in particular the feasibility of a form of change in the *administered world* through the thought of Herbert Marcuse. In particular, we will focus on the relations between biology and society, stressing, within an overall political view, how habits could be connected to emancipation's processes. In the last part of the essay the concept of *critical learning* of a *Habitus* will be deepened. The theme of Learning and Dis-learning, understood in a broad sense, can go back to being the unifying centre of the theme of the transformation of the existent. In particular, attention will be paid not to the *Habitus* that has been already acquired and that is still acting in the bodies and in society, but to *early learning phases* of new *Habitus*, that is, to the process of their "incorporation". The hypotheses is that if this process occurs in learning environments opened to corporeality and to the biological features of the bodies, but also opened with the relational and pre-social aspects – rather than individualizing and only self-performing or self-empowerment ways of being – perhaps it could be possible to find a key to differently think the forms of automation that nowadays deeply shape our lives, both individual then social.

1. *Habitus/hexis*

In this paper we shall examine the concept of *habitus* in relation to its possible variations in terms of individual and collective behaviour changes. The concept of *habitus* in current philosophical debate has taken on a special urgency because of its political and ethical implications. Individual and collective behavioural

responses and patterns appear more than ever homogenous, standardised, repetitive and compulsive, made all the more cogent, compelling and binding thanks to a diffuse digital environment, as pointed out by Bernard Stiegler in his seminal work, *La société automatique*¹. *Habitus*, learned, incorporated and interiorised, is today, after Foucault, what can be termed a *subjection device* or, as Bourdieu would say, a *matrix of repetition*.

Habitus situates itself somewhere between the social and the physical-corporeal; the point of juncture of these two spheres deserves investigation if we are to try and understand how and in what ways always identical and repetitive behavioural schema may be de-automated. An overview of some of the essential philosophical notions involved in the theory of *habitus* that can help us better comprehend what constitutes the social-corporeal *milieu*, or rather the intersection of the natural with the artificial, where *habitus* as such is formed, is a useful starting point in our discussion.

From a certain point of view, Aristotle's notion of *hexis* in connection with learning may be said to incorporate dual aspects of the singular body and of social schema. Habit (*hexis*) is highly valued in the *Nicomachean Ethics*, where a recurrent action is deemed as being possibly conducive to virtue (*areté*). *Hexis*, that may be constructed as an *habitual state* or *way of being*, is an acquired disposition susceptible to transformative upgrading; as much as any sort of action may in itself be devoid of moral content, social practice and use can structure and reinforce it positively by way of approval to the point of exemplifying and instantiating ethical principles². Body-wise, then, *hexis* may be said to implement automaticity of response, inducing gestural repetition that even if learned becomes 'natural', embodied, that is, as second nature.

Actually, we should note that Aristotle never uses the term 'second nature' as such in any of his works. It is rather in the Aristotelian *vulgata*, especially in scholasticism, but even earlier in the Roman world – Cicero, for instance³ – that his concept of 'habit' is construed as equivalent to that of 'second nature'. In fact, terms such as *secunda natura* or, more often, *altera natura* are mistakenly attributed to him. When he discusses the concept of 'habit', Aristotle is instead careful to refer to it only as *almost natural*, or *similar to nature*. For instance, in *Rhetoric*: «what has become habit now happens by nature, since habit is something similar to nature»⁴; in *On memory and reminiscence*: «habit

¹ See B. Stiegler, *La société automatique*, Paris 2015.

² See Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, 1144a 26-28. Cfr. P.-M. Morel, *L'habitude: une seconde nature?* in *Aristote et la notion de nature, Enjeux épistémologiques et pratiques* (ed. P.-M. Morel), Bordeaux 1997, pp. 131-148, and Th. C. Lockwood, *Habituation, Habit and Character in Aristotle's "Nicomachean Ethics"*, in T. Sparrow, A. Hutchinson (eds.) *A History of Habit. From Aristotle to Bourdieu*, Lanham 2013, pp. 19-36; P. Rodrigo, *La dynamique de l'"hexis" chez Aristote. L'état, la tenue et la limite*, «Alter», 12, 2004, pp. 11-25; C. Carlisle, *The Question of Habit in Theology and Philosophy*, «Mind & Society», 19, 2013 (2-3), pp. 30-57, showing the heritage of *hexis* concept in several successive philosophical strands (both French and German).

³ See Cicero, *De natura deorum*, II, LX, 152, in *Opere politiche e filosofiche*, vol. III, Torino 2007, p. 327 e ss.

⁴ Aristotle, *Rhetoric*, I, 11, 1370 a 6-7, in Id., *Retorica*, Milano 1996, p. 87.

is already like nature»⁵. However, while Aristotle appears in *Rhetoric* to be keen to maintain the subtle distinction between natural and second-natural, that is between invariable occurrences, that belong to the realm of the immutable (what happens «often»)⁶, and frequent or recurrent occurrences, that belong to the realm of the changeable, he nevertheless does postulate in places that regularity in the repetition of an act – that is an habitual act – somehow sets up behavioural patterns with a compelling natural or physical bias, going so far as to declare that «what happens often generates a nature»⁷.

Hexis may be said to be natural in so far as it is deemed integral to human nature, which ‘naturally’ stretches out to encompass the virtual. For any disposition to actually make the transition from the artificial to the natural, however, requires routine practice and ongoing repetition, that is, what Marcel Mauss refers to as *anthropotechnics*. For any learned action to be accommodated within the natural sphere of human behaviour there must in some way be habituation. Higher order virtuous actions thus come to be performed smoothly and effortlessly without prejudice to lower order procedural automatism and procedural memory-governed mechanical functions. They are indeed so deeply incorporated and imbedded as to be almost akin to hard-wiring; they are performed without their having to be given a second thought (‘thoughtlessly’), hence naturally, within the framework of a ‘physics of the body’. As has been argued, «habit is a movement, which has become natural, through which man responds to the incompleteness of his nature»⁸.

Habits, understood as acquired behavioural patterns, therefore, start out as something not natural which through repetition and routinization become quasi-natural. Quasi because as much as they may turn into an incorporated automatism, they nevertheless retain aspects of artificiality. The fluency and proficiency accompanying habitual behaviour are the stuff of which artifice is made of. The growing ability to perform that comes with repetition and routinization, maybe increasing self-deception even, is a prerequisite of any *techne* or *skill*, though Aristotle does not go so far as to claim as much. But what’s important to bear in mind for the purpose of the present discussion is that, as already stated, Aristotle never considers habit to be fully equatable with the natural, as close as it may come to seeming so, for *hexis is both nature and not-nature*⁹. Moving on from this premise the question now arises as to where the evasive transitional element of resistance to naturalisation, of ‘counter-naturalness’ in the process of any behaviour ‘becoming natural’ situates itself. More importantly, what are we confronted with or what occurs at this transformational crossover point of the artificial and the natural? The answer of course is learning.

⁵ Aristotle, *De memoria et reminiscencia*, 2, 452 a 29-30.

⁶ See *Rhet.*, I. 11, 1370 a 8-9.

⁷ See *De mem.*, 2, 452 b 1.

⁸ P.-M. Morel, *L’habitude: une seconde nature?*, cit., p. 135.

⁹ M. Piazza, *Creature dell’abitudine*, cit., pp. 9-10 and pp. 37-42.

Thus Aristotle: «Therefore, the difference between being used immediately, from an early age, in one way rather than another is not small; on the contrary, there is a huge difference, indeed it is everything»¹⁰. We are not so much concerned here in analysing repetition from an ontological point of view. Rather, what interests us in this statement is that it draws attention to the paramount importance of the initial, hesitant movement of the repeated gesture, when behaviour has not yet solidified into a fully automated or routinized pattern¹¹. This raises a number of interesting questions: at what point does gestural reiteration turn into a systematic order making for a standardised set of behavioural responses; how does a recurrent gesture get reinforced to the point of becoming an habitual state; where lies the fountainhead of *hexis*, understood as a way of *being*; what does it start out as and how is it consolidated? In other words, Aristotle's remark here is interesting because it focuses our attention on the initial, seminal stages of *hexis*, when it has not yet appropriated our subjectivity in the process of structuring us as subjects. It is at these incipient stages of *hexis* that *resistance to naturalization* may still be observed. In its infancy, before morphing into 'second nature' and holding sway over our subjectivity, *hexis* has to contend with 'first nature'. This entanglement of the acquired and the natural leads us to reconsider the relationship between subject and body. In particular, the concept of corporeity in the constitutively moulding dynamics of 'education' and 'training', in the many senses in which these terms are used, comes to take centre stage in furthering the discussion.

Aristotle's quasi-equivalence of habit and second nature along with the basic ambiguity between negative-restraining value and positive-forming value, between conquered regularity and subjecting mechanicity are themes that under various guises have feed into Western culture and fuelled philosophical debate down through the centuries. Cicero, for instance, speaks of *consuetudo*, Thomas Aquinas of *habitus*, while *custom* is a key concept in the ethical-political debates of French moralism. In his *Essays*, Montaigne devotes considerable attention to the concept of habit, also referred to as *coutume* or *accoutumance*; «habit is second nature, and no less powerful»¹², he contends. And, by way of almost prefiguring Foucault, he then goes on to discuss power's equivocal status as both a factor of emancipation and subjugation, along with the imperious potency of repetition as an internal, intimate *ratio* of the disciplinary device. But it is perhaps Pascal, in the *Thoughts*, who most resolutely avers «habit is our nature»¹³. But in his typical style, Pascal problematizes the issue of the natural versus the artificial, hypothesizing a sort of reversibility between natural and second-natural: «habit is second nature, which destroys the first. But what is nature? Why is habit not

¹⁰ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book II, 1103b 1104a.

¹¹ On pedagogy understood as 'applied mechanics', starting from Aristotle point of view and going to anthropotechnics perspective, cfr. P. Sloterdijk, *Du mußt dein Leben ändern*. Über Anthropotechnik, Frankfurt 2009.

¹² M. de Montaigne, *Essais* (éd. A. Tournon), Paris 1997-98, p. 1877 (III, 10).

¹³ B. Pascal, *Pensées* (eds. Chevalier), Paris 1962, p. 221-22 (149).

natural? I really fear that this nature is itself only a first habit, just as habit is a second nature»¹⁴. Here is deconstruction ahead of its time! Where does nature end and human construction begin?

Pascal's quandary as to the blurred boundaries between these two realms, generally keeping safely each to its own in standard philosophical debate, raises a further question as to where the domain of matters ethical and moral situates itself *vis-à-vis* that of unreflective, automatically engendered actions springing from our deep-seated animality. And on from that, how does the structuring of an habitual gesture through repetitive practise go into making and becoming *habitus*? How does habituation move up from repetitious body work through to a structured automatic behaviour pattern and then onto a fully fledged, inured social custom? And, moving back down the other way, what is actually meant when we speak of the artificial *becoming body* or *becoming natural*? In confronting these knotty issues, Pascal's reasoning is truly remarkable: «What are our natural principles, if not the principles of our habit [...]? A different habit will give us other natural principles, which can be seen from experience»¹⁵. But if there are some natural principles «that cannot be erased by habit, there are also those created by habit against nature»¹⁶: some habits have their own specific strength of repetition that self-induces a change in the current habit, a variation (*clinamen*) of the operating tendency (*conatus*), that is, of the program we are executing.

2. Repetition, corporal schema and difference in Maurice Merleau-Ponty

Given the above it comes as no surprise that Bourdieu, one of the major contemporary theoreticians of *habitus*, has conducted an important study on the works of Pascal: *Méditations pascaliennes*¹⁷. We are justified then in leaping forward several centuries to discuss Bourdieu's views on *habitus* not, however, before taking a look at Merleau-Ponty's concept of corporeity. This concept will be used here as referring to a point of convergence of the 'primary' – natural and deeply vital – automatism in response to stimulus, as discussed in *The Structure of Behaviour*¹⁸, and of repetition qua second nature, as dealt with in *Phenomenology of perception*¹⁹, with reference to habit and fundamental body scheme. Of special relevance to our discussion are the pages dealing with *habitude* in relation to the *corps propre*; here Merleau-Ponty contends that every repetition, every movement that has become habitual, that is to say automatic in the procedural sense, is a form of passivity, notwithstanding the persistence

¹⁴ Ivi, p. 74 (120).

¹⁵ *Ibid.* (119).

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ See P. Bourdieu, *Méditations pascaliennes*, Paris 1997.

¹⁸ See M. Merleau-Ponty, *La structure du comportement* (1942), Paris 2018.

¹⁹ See M. Merleau-Ponty, *Phénoménologie de la perception* (1945), Paris 2012.

of some activity²⁰. Equally important is the attention given by Merleau-Ponty to the primarily inter-subjective and proto-social value of bodily repetitions; Self, as he points out, is typically and consistently immersed in «an intersubjective field, not despite my body and my historical situation, but vice versa being this body, this situation and everything else through them»²¹.

In short, it may be said that in Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology, the body is viewed as a machine automatically reproducing behavioural responses, starting from elementary motor schema and moving up to *become* more complex patterns, capable of affecting the social and political sphere. What's more, despite such automaticity, as already said Merleau-Ponty allows for the possibility of change to occur from within the system. All told then, in Merleau-Ponty habit and in perspective *habitus* are primarily linked to body performance, and more precisely to reiterative bodily action, the groundwork out of which grows the repetitive behaviour of the subject, constitutive of the subject itself.

The ambiguous relationship tying the lived-living body of *Leib*, with its active and passive components, to the body-object of *Körper* is that of a contradictory contemporaneity between a *vehicle of automatisms* of routinized response patterns, the forerunners of *habitus*, and an *element of resistance* to that repetition that makes for our experience of free-flowing continuity. Without this *internal productive resistance*, *Leib's* recurring divergence would in fact be subjectively indiscernible. Action-structuring schemata, then, is susceptible to change.

It is within this framework that learning *through* and *by* repetition acquires special significance. Learning in this context means acquiring new patterns of behaviour, new habits; in a word, learning is *habitus* changing, all of which is rooted in concrete, on-going body dynamics, allowing for different individual and even collective reactions to diverse environmental stimuli. Viewed from this angle, «learning never means becoming capable of repeating the same gesture, but rather of providing the situation with an adequate response by different means. And it is no longer correct to say that the reaction is acquired towards an individual situation. Instead, it is a new attitude to solve a series of problems that have the same form»²².

In the same movement, we learn to repeat but also to resist repetition, resistance revealing itself in the act of repetition as both friction, during effectual motor phases, and *strength* (or *effort*)²³, during the learning of a new passivity or, in Mauss's terms, of new *techniques of the body*. Because of this concurrence, a sort of memory of the resistant gesture (i.e. in counter-phase) with respect to

²⁰ See M. Merleau-Ponty, *Phénoménologie de la perception*, cit., the whole sections *La motricité du corps propre* and *La synthèse du corps propre*, ivi, pp. 127-190.

²¹ Ivi, p. 516.

²² M. Merleau-Ponty, *La structure du comportement*, cit., p. 147.

²³ The reference here goes to Main de Birain (the plexus resistance-and-effort in the repeated gesture, which is 'productive' of novelty), see M. Merleau-Ponty, *L'union de l'âme et du corps. Chez Malebranche, Biran et Bergson*, Paris 1997.

what is being performed 'automatically' continues to persist in newly acquired motor patterns. 'Veering' (*clinamen*) from the inertial condition, this act of self-preservation comes to take on a new shape. As Merleau-Ponty makes clear, «the perspective presentation of objects is not understandable except through the resistance of my body to any variation in perspective»²⁴. And what applies to visual perception also goes for any perceptual dynamic. We *have and are* habit, that is, habit understood as variable repetition, as irresolute pattern. Proneness to (*power for*) self-differentiation in repetition is inherent in the dynamics of one's own body. The body has and is repetition: it «is the primordial habit (*habitude*), the habit that conditions all the others and thanks to which they are understandable»²⁵.

We have seen, then, how tightly body, repetition and variation are locked in with one another. From a phenomenological point of view, none would have or make any *sense* without the other two. Corporeity is then materially and consequentially the natural, indeed the 'bi-natural', locus of any *sensible pattern* of our behaviours, in so far as corporeity is both nature and second nature. The theoretical and political upshots of such an approach call for attention, even if only briefly.

The 'close-to-the-bone' association of repetition and difference represents the ontogenetic core of all learning. As such, the aforementioned triple association is already the most relevant form of learning itself, absolutely decisive for the overall meaning of (our) future gesture, understood in its *aptitude to de-automate itself*. *Learning to unlearn* lies precisely here, in these indeterminate body plexuses at odd with one another, the vying of which allows for dissension to emerge. And, within it, the space for any possible dissension.

We have so far discussed the key role of the body in habit forming and reforming. Our attention, though, needs at this point to be given briefly to the subject. The subject can only be successor to these psycho-corporeal dynamics; in relation to the specificity of the *habitus* à la Bourdieu, this procedural unconscious or even a social unconscious, if you like, takes precedence. But the subject *remains* as a figure of organization of the impulse (*conatus*) that moves the body. Likewise, in their progressive socio-cultural articulations, habits are structured and extended up and out to the social sphere, moving away from the bio-corporeal level. Passivity and institution²⁶ have at this point transformed incipient 'body primacy' into an automatism of reproduction of abstract schemes, of ritual forms, as in Bourdieu's *habitus*. Be it as it may, the fact nevertheless remains that this second nature would immediately be destitute of meaning if it weren't considered in relationship to *Leib*. As with the 'lowest' organic tier of the body, then, so for the 'highest' tier of the social-cultural.

Taking up again from Merleau-Ponty, the organism is also confronted with a pattern as it learns and repeats its own elementary behaviour, establishing a

²⁴ M. Merleau-Ponty, *Phénoménologie de la perception*, cit., p. 121.

²⁵ Ivi, p. 120.

²⁶ See M. Merleau-Ponty, *L'institution, la passivité*, Paris 2003.

'divergent' automatism. Even at its most rudimentary, the organism 'is' repetition. Every organism is subject to repetition patterns, as also the fully-fledged individual and, more extensively, the social organism as a whole. Reacting to stimuli, the organism is passivized by automatisms but, *at the same time*, it *produces a response* to the stimulus that is not only automatic. Through its response it is in fact already *making sense*, thus gaining latitude to accommodate for critical learning and for the construction of an action and a scheme: «the organism [...] cannot be compared to a keyboard on which external stimuli would be exercised and on which they would define their own form, and this for the simple reason that the organism contributes to constituting this form»²⁷. From this point of view, repetition – more precisely, the repeated response – is a plastic reproduction of the pattern that *we are*, and that partially and empirically adapts to the environment; it is a repetition *inhabited* by a space that makes it possible in advance to meet the future pattern that we are learning in action, of which we do not 'see' (in the sense of *theorein*) clearly the outline, but which organizes our entire action, both individual and social. Such a standpoint clearly does away with any reductionist view of the stimulus. Elucidating on his conception of the stimulus, Merleau-Ponty points out that any stimulus «often acts much less for its elementary properties than for its spatial distribution, its rhythm or the rhythm of its intensity. More generally: it happens very often that the effect of a complex stimulus is not predictable starting from the elements that compose it»²⁸. Viewed from Merleau-Ponty's angle – but also from that of current theories of *habitus*²⁹ – every learning process, including 'upper' grade ones, as far as those involving complex cultural frameworks, has a distinct biological matrix grounded in an organism's responses, going to make up elaborate behaviour patterns. If so, it is not inapposite to regard the stimulus-response mechanism as a sort of 'natural prehistory' of second nature. As we shall more fully see further on, this sort of reasoning can also be encountered in Marcuse.

From what we've so far seen, a *variant engendering device* is wholly conceivable and viable within a stimulus-response sequence perspective, essentially not unlike the '0-1' digital model from which so many crucial current social automatisms have sprung. Habit forming and reforming or deforming would therefore appear to be 'consubstantial', as the routinised and recurrent regularity of a habit and hence of *habitus* up as far as socio-politically consolidated regularities, is 'ruffled' by a primal internal articulation which gives rise to an intrinsic, self-diversionary

²⁷ M. Merleau-Ponty, *La structure du comportement*, cit., p. 13.

²⁸ Ivi, p. 10.

²⁹ See the recent I. Testa, F. Caruana (eds.), *Habits. Pragmatist Approaches from Cognitive Science, Neuroscience, and Social Theory*, Cambridge 2020, but also other studies specific on the role of plasticity in repetition, like *Habits: plasticity, learning and freedom* (J. Bernacer, J. A. Lombo, J. I. Murillo eds.), «Frontiers in Human Neuroscience», 2015 (on line). Of interest, on the concept of 'double unconscious' in relation to habits, also T. Possamai, *Inconscio e ripetizione. La fabbrica della soggettività*, Milano 2016 and, for an overall analysis, I. Pelgrefi, *Filosofia dell'automatismo*, Salerno-Napoli 2018.

and natural faculty, capable of differentiation from the same operating schema by passivizing the agent 'organism' simultaneously to its acting.

3. *Habitus*: notes on Pierre Bourdieu and Marcel Mauss

The devices of repetition we've so far been examining are consequential well beyond the strictly corporeal, reaching out to the inter-subjective and social spheres. Merleau-Ponty is aware of such an impingement, even though he never fully pursues the issue. Bourdieu's use of the term *habitus*, while owing much to Merleau-Ponty's theory of *habitude*, better highlights, however, these broader implications. Bourdieu's critique draws attention moreover to objective elements of theoretical-formal analogy between *body schema* and *habitus*³⁰. He in fact describes *habitus* as a

system of lasting and transferable dispositions which, integrating all past experiences, functions at all times as a matrix of perceptions, evaluations and actions, and makes it possible to fulfil infinitely different problems having the same form and thanks to the incessant corrections of the results obtained, which are themselves produced dialectically by those results³¹.

The interesting point here is that *habitus* may be understood as an *automatic repetition device*. And yet, it also makes room for inherent change, operating like an intellectual motor scheme that while arranging in advance for any action to be reiterated over time, and thus routinized, provides nevertheless also for future departure from the standardised pattern. Bourdieu's reference to 'perceptions', 'learning', 'pattern' and '*shape of stimuli*' vis-à-vis the environment, with which in fact *habitus* is deemed to ceaselessly interact, clearly betrays the Merleau-Pontian derivation of the concept. If *habitus* has, in its most general form, a social origin, this is in the sense of an incorporation of patterns, of techniques of the body often acting at the unconscious level, therefore outside the rational control of the Subject, understood in its broadest possible meaning, that is to say of the many-tiered Subject, including its political and collective instantiations, as Bourdieu's use of the concept of class suggests. In other words, Bourdieu's interpretation brings into clearer focus *habitus* as an essentially 'dynamic structure of ambiguity', discharging its function both *actively* and *passively*. From this angle *habitus* may be said to process incoming external stimuli, 'repeating' them and simultaneously giving rise to unexpected forms. Such a process clearly

³⁰ See L. Wacquant, *Breve genealogia e anatomia del concetto di habitus*, «ANUAC», 4, 2015 (2), pp. 67-77; C. Piazzesi, *Abitudine e potere. Da Pascal a Bourdieu*, Pisa 2003; T. Sparrow, A. Hutchinson, *A History of Habit. From Aristotle to Bourdieu*, cit.; see also E. Grosz, *Habit Today: Ravaisson, Bergson, Deleuze and Us*, «Body & Society», 19, 2013, pp. 217-239, where habits, read as a *contraction that preserves*, it is then naturally prolonged in that property of the *habitus* that consists – as well as in Merleau-Ponty – in being an *extension of the contracted habits*.

³¹ P. Bourdieu, *Esquisse d'une théorie de la pratique*, Genève 1972, p. 211.

then complexifies the institution of the identical, that is, it complexifies the establishment of any social behaviour, in so far as *habitus* comes to be conceived of as a «lastingly generating principle of regulated improvisations»³². What's of interest in the current discussion is the improvisation of routine-breaking behaviour springing from abiding *habitus*, that is of how innovative behaviour patterns dwell within and arise not so much despite of but indeed thanks to and out of repetition, in other words, as Bourdieu has it, of how new forms of behaviour inhabit repetition (semantic plexuses much used by Bourdieu to be borne in mind concerning this argument being *habitat*, *habitus*, *inhabiting*). Bourdieu's clear sense of the cohabitation of this 'odd couple', is enough in itself to restore the more properly philosophical issues at stake in the present paper, without overlooking the fact that even for Merleau-Ponty understanding the sense of improvisation of the organism was already a key issue.

In fact, as much as the over-determined dynamic between repetition and difference certainly applies to *habitus* in the social domain, it cannot be overlooked that at the same time this dynamic is rooted in significant physical states of the body and in circumstances befalling it, in the body's silences even, not to speak of its ambiguous and relational extensions with other bodies; in short, there is no *habitus* without incorporation. As can be seen, we are here once again confronted with the classical and recurrent issue of the relationship between nature and history. From this angle, it can be argued that *habitus* is the expression, in directly ethical-political terms, of Merleau-Ponty's 'bodily unconscious' and of its inherent power. Yet it is thanks to this power that the body passivized by *habitus* exhibits its ability to passively resist and counter the cogency and constancy of any *habitus*. Here then, we have in the same stroke power and resistance: the enduring (*conatus*) of oneself within difference (*clinamen*). Thus considered, nature eschews total culturalisation via *habitus*, resisting, like a shadow of negativity that can never be fully retracted from the device called *habitus*. Take this short passage, in which the whole Bourdieusian discourse is framed between, on the one hand, an history that becomes nature (precisely in the *habitus*), and on the other in the concept of 'world in the world', that is a structured system of reversible relationships that closely resembles the fact that the body scheme, in Merleau-Ponty, «is a system open to the world, correlative to the world»³³: «As history made nature (*histoire faite nature*), [*habitus*] is what gives practices their relative autonomy from the external determinations of the immediate present. This autonomy is that of the past, put into action and agent which, functioning as accumulated capital, produces history starting from history and thus ensures the permanence in the change that makes the individual agent a world in the world»³⁴.

³² P. Bourdieu, *Méditations pascaliennes*, cit., pp. 250.

³³ M. Merleau-Ponty, *Phénoménologie de la perception*, cit., p. 179, footnote 1.

³⁴ P. Bourdieu, *Le Sens pratique*, Paris 1980, p. 90.

A formula according to which *habitus* is «history made nature»³⁵ becomes truly understandable only if we think of the intrinsic relationship between *habitus* and body, as has been posited here; the body, and not the Subject, is what makes for the simultaneous connection of nature and history. Of course, the visual angle from which we are examining the concept of *habitus* is undoubtedly partial, but it allows us to think that the socio-corporeal process of dis-automatisation is linked to the non-programmable, nor controllable diversions of bodies, understood as bodies engaged in the practices of resistance and transformation of the world. «*Habitus* contributes to transforming what transforms it»³⁶, just as *Leib* is able to modify his own body schema.

Examining the use of the term *habitus* in Bourdieu's early writings, along with references made to Mauss's 'social anthropology', is helpful in better appreciating how tightly Bourdieu deems *habitus* to be bound up with the domain of the body. One of its earliest appearances is in the 1962 essay *Celibat et condition paysanne*³⁷. Here *habitus* is used to refer to the «motor habits»³⁸ of the farmers of the Pyrenean village of Denguin. As such, it is associated from the start with the *body in motion in relation to social space*, as repetition in relation to introjection³⁹. The future evolution of the concept seems to be here already fully encapsulated. Such clarity of conception is epitomised in the description Bourdieu makes of how the farmer learns a new dance, differing from the usual one; his action is portrayed as an unconscious learning of what is *becoming natural* in the dance movement. This becoming natural is in fact equivalent to *second nature*, so much so that in addition to *habitus* Bourdieu also employs the Aristotelian term *hexis*. The term *habitus* is from the outset and even at its fledgling stage used by Bourdieu with reference to how bodies, in their relational and multiple dimension, circumscribe every *mutation of the habitus in the habitus*. Bourdieu strongly endorses the idea of the quasi-physical nature of any mutation, for it is «a real change of 'nature', since bodily habits are what is most naturally experienced, and on which conscious action has no influence»⁴⁰. Bourdieu is beholden to Mauss's essay *Techniques of the body*⁴¹ for his initial use of the term, which he will however work on and develop over the years for his own purposes. But for our purposes it is useful to stop and take a closer look here at Mauss's use of the term.

According to Mauss «Each society has its own special habits (*habitudes*)»⁴². Their exceptionality is such as to practically define any given society in its

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ *Ivi*, pp. 156-157.

³⁷ See P. Bourdieu, *Celibat et condition paysanne*, «Etudes Rurales», 5-6, 1962, pp. 32-135.

³⁸ *Ivi*, p. 99.

³⁹ Notably, in its being the differential between citizen and farmer, the latter is somehow 'subjected' to the 'model' or the 'scheme' of the former. See p. 100.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

⁴¹ M. Mauss, *Techniques of the body* (1934), tr. B. Brewster, «Economy and Society», 2, 1973, pp. 70-88.

⁴² *Ivi*, p. 72.

entirety. What makes for *habitudes* to be so cogent and all pervasive is ‘social repetition’. Our attention here is drawn first and foremost to the concept of ‘repetition’, for it is through repetition, grounded in essentially physical bodily practices and procedures (techniques of the body), that *habitus* comes to be characterised and structured. It is in fact in analysing a number of everyday ‘behaviours’, including walking, swimming, dancing and gradually up to eating, sleeping or sexual reproduction – where Mauss focuses on such issues as their *learning*, their *variable execution* (the learned pattern changes during the exercise) and their *transmissibility* – that the concept of *habitus* comes to be foregrounded. Here too, in some way, the behavioural technique produces the human, in the double reciprocal relationship in which repetition is installed between biological corporeality and social schema.

According to Mauss, *habitus* «expresses, infinitely better than ‘habit (*habitude*)’, the ‘hexis’, the ‘experience’ and the ‘faculty’ of Aristotle (who was a psychologist)»⁴³; this is because *habitus* is *exposed* to the technical form of a repetition exerted on an element that has always been both social and linked to the historical-concrete dimension of the body. *Habitus*, in fact, «designate those metaphysical *habitudes*, that mysterious ‘memory’, the subjects of volumes or short and famous theses. These ‘habits’ do not just vary with individuals and their imitations, they vary especially between societies, educations, proprieties and fashions, prestige. In them we should see the techniques and work of collective and individual practical reason rather than, in the ordinary way, merely the soul and its repetitive faculties»⁴⁴.

What becomes evident here is that there is clearly an original link between repetition, body and *habitus*. Viewed from this middle ground – where *habitus*’s technical characteristics as a social technique clearly emerge and can be seen to intercept with the technical aspects congenital to *Leib* – we can better appreciate how consequential the concept of repetition is in Mauss: «we are dealing with techniques of the body. The body is man’s first and most natural instrument. [...] man’s first and most natural technical object, and at the same time technical means, is his body [...]. Before instrumental techniques there is the ensemble of techniques of the body»⁴⁵.

Given as much, it is safe to contend that at a theoretical level Bourdieu’s *habitus* can comfortably accommodate Merleau-Ponty’s concept of corporeality and Mauss’s *techniques du corps* as agents for change. Finally, it is worth noting that Bourdieu’s *habitus* does not eschew the political, as when the author turns his attention to considering the eventuation of changes in the existing state of affairs, discussing the issue very much along the lines of a critique of second nature.

⁴³ Ivi, p. 73.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

⁴⁵ Ivi, pp. 75-76.

4. Second nature and capitalism in Herbert Marcuse

The historical-philosophical debate on second nature was indeed widespread in the 70s. The topical concept was related to many other issues strongly debated at the time such as standardisation, addiction to consumer society, and the so-called *naturalization of capitalism* in the Marxian sense. In the wider societal critique of the time there was the awareness that for the capitalist system to function as smoothly as possible the social meaning of commodities – not the least of which the human element itself – as well as of the work required for their production had to be concealed. The best means for achieving this dissemblance was seen to reside precisely in the mechanisms attending *habitus*. The question of whether there's any room in the current philosophical debate around capitalist repetition for issues relating to corporeality is especially meaningful when viewed from within the theoretical framework of the '70s debate. Notwithstanding that the body as an 'object' of study is no stranger to modern-day philosophical discussions, it may be asked what exactly is its role in the debate? Does it risk becoming a sideline in the theory, downgraded to a pre-cultural 'stimulus' without any significant social consequence; is it running the risk of being deemed as something belonging to the sphere of pre- or indeed a-social phenomena? Theoretical debate is now at a juncture that requires rethinking the process of *un-learning habitus* which takes place and has its place in the ambiguous relationship between [first] nature and second nature, giving rise to unprecedented forms of behaviour. Indeed, the ambiguity itself linking the two natures calls for closer scrutiny if its exact status and role in the process is to be better understood, no less than do basal stimulus or instinctual automatism.

At this point it is worth turning to Marcuse, writing at about the same time as Bourdieu, to help clarify some of the issues involved here. Of particular interest for our discussion is one of his early essays published in 1969, *A biological foundation for socialism?*⁴⁶, which consummately conveys his overall views on the matter very well. Here, Marcuse discusses whether and to what extent the social reproduction of domination, as well as its disestablishment, can have a biological underpinning. Bearing in mind what has been said thus far, there should be no doubt at this stage as to the key role played by *habitus* as the means and medium through which dominion is transmitted and reproduced. Linguistic differences aside, Marcuse turns to the concept of *second nature* to provide an answer to his query, alert to the fact that the 'critical' and *necessarily ambiguous* relationship in which body, repetition and dis-learning are enmeshed is the nub and hub of the matter.

True to form, Marcuse holds no punches, laying his condemnatory cards clearly out on the table from the start: «The so-called consumer economy and the politics of corporate capitalism have created a second nature of man which

⁴⁶ H. Marcuse, *A biological foundation for socialism?*, in Id., *An Essay On Liberation*, Princeton 1969, pp. 12-21.

ties him libidinally and aggressively to the commodity form»⁴⁷. Indictment aside, what interests us here of Marcuse's critique of consumer society – where, needless to say, consumption is not least consumption of bodies and therefore of our ground-zero *nature* itself – is the link between corporeality and *habitus*, or rather between *biological organism* and the *capitalist subjugation device*. As problematic – or opaque, even – as this link may appear, it warrants close scrutiny if we are to come to philosophical grips with the very feasibility of habits changing; the question confronting us is whether there is any leeway for changes to occur in second nature at its first nature interface, given that the subject is fully caught up – we might say 'entangled' or 'emmeshed' – in the interaction between the two natures, regardless of the terms we choose to talk about this liaison, this interchange, be it as 'matter' and 'spirit', singularity and society, and why not, in the wake of Bourdieu, as 'nature' and 'history'.

Marcuse is clear from the outset as to where the bedrock lies, flatly positing an «organic foundation of morality, in the human being»⁴⁸. Presuming morality to be, at least to some extent, firmly grounded in the body – if not indeed at a yet more inchoate organic level – and not in the subject, leaves open the question as to how morality can well up and grow into a fully fledged and articulate, personally experienced and socially sanctioned system. Such crypto-Nietzschean postulations crop up throughout Marcuse's works. By putting the body centre stage, Marcuse would appear to throw the classical dichotomy of subject-bound political criticism versus subject-free utopian liberation off-kilter. For sure, if we are to go along with the idea that «political radicalism implies a moral radicalism: the emergence of a morality that can pre-condition man to freedom»⁴⁹ in the sense that «even before being adapted to specific social criteria [...] morality is a '*disposition*' of the organism»⁵⁰, a lot of familiar philosophical givens call for reviewing and rethinking from a different angle. Note here how once again how mind-setting *disposition* is not subject-borne but rooted in the physical organism. The same *habitus* or schema engendering relationship between subject and corporeity already encountered in both Merleau-Ponty and Bourdieu comes out here when Marcuse speculates that morality as '*disposition*' is «perhaps rooted in the erotic drive»⁵¹.

A first comment. In this narrow round of propositions, Marcuse postulates the existence of a device – not all that different from Foucault's biopolitical device – of a scheme, of a second nature so deep-seated as to *forego* device set up itself. It may be asked what we are dealing with here: history or nature? Actually, the question in these terms misses the point; what we are confronted with at this level of analysis is far more complex. The pertinent question is: what, if anything, does something we have chosen to call 'second nature' have to do

⁴⁷ *Ivi*, p. 14.

⁴⁸ *Ivi*, p. 13.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

⁵¹ *Ibid.*

with vital automatism, basic compulsions to repetition, and primary impulses themselves? Needless to say, as outlined in his *Eros and civilization*, Marcuse has no doubts as to the erotic nature of the primeval impulse. But his treatment is theoretically far more consequential than your standard 'eros-be-all-and-end-all' fare. In fact, he does not assign the erotic impulse to the realm of vitalistic irrationalism, placing it instead at an intermediate proto-organizational level. From the outset, Marcuse is clear as to the fact that there is an «instinctual foundation for solidarity among human beings»⁵². Indeed, a bit further down the line he squarely talks of the existence of a sort of «instinctual structure»⁵³.

The issues raised in the excerpts referred to above are deserving of closer scrutiny and discussion; suffice it to draw attention here to the fact that in Marcuse's scheme of things, the organism, with its unreflective and instinctual automatism, and the 'structuring of the impulse', that is the formation of a *second nature*, all share a common ground. In their mutual ongoing intercept each seems to summon the other. In this sense, the *instinctual foundation* is also «historical» in so far as «the malleability of 'human nature' reaches into the depth of man's instinctual structure»⁵⁴. Likewise, «changes in morality may 'sink down' into the 'biological' dimension and modify organic behavior»⁵⁵.

In Marcuse's view as set out in *Eros and civilization*, the feasibility itself of the 'Revolution', indeed its very viability, lies precisely in the turbulent, unrestrainable 'meeting of the waters' of the organic-instinctual with the institutional, criss-crossed by the undercurrents of repetition patterns. It is in fact in this very materially concrete locus, which is at the same time caught up in 'history', that un-learning of the all-pervasive, all-intrusive institutions of capitalism can take place. Consistent with what has been argued so far, the ambiguity or undecidability characterising this intermediate area between body and society can be seen to be an essential enabler of mind-set change:

I use the terms 'biological' and 'biology' not in the sense of the scientific discipline, but in order to designate the process and the dimension in which inclinations, behavior patterns, and aspirations become vital needs [...]. We could then speak, for example, of the biological need of freedom, or of some aesthetic needs as having taken root in the organic structure of man, in his 'nature', or rather 'second nature'⁵⁶.

This last quote points not only to the relevance in the un-learning process of 'historical truth' but also to that of the biological, of second nature, or, more precisely, of the paradoxical *becoming natural* of instinctual arousal intersecting with the organism's reaction to stimuli. Notwithstanding that here as elsewhere Marcuse acknowledges desire to be delusively and deceptively unreliable, easily misleading the subject as to its centrality and supremacy – even if self-consciously

⁵² Ivi, p. 13.

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ Ivi, p. 14.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, footnote 1.

unaware, the subject is in fact always constructed/reified -, the instinctual is always at work oiling the wheels of possible un-learning.

5. Learning a new *habitus*: a form of critique?

In view of the foregoing, then, it can safely be assumed that un-learning sits comfortably and securely on the instinctual. The question remaining to be answered, however, is what shape, what *Gestalt* the un-learning process may take. Some aspects of the role played by the body in behaviour pattern variance have already been discussed. What precisely is learning?; what do we mean when speak of the *critical learning* of a *habitus*?; how can a truly critical attitude grow out of repetition?; are questions we must now endeavour to answer. Rather than to already acquired and incorporated *habitus*, attention, we believe, should be given to the *habitus* phasing in and instalment stage if we are to try to answer them. What occurs at the moment of *habitus* incorporation, that is when *habitus* is 'learnt', is where the focus should be. The crucially consequential moment is not when *habitus* is supposedly already securely seated behind the wheel, steering and driving the subject where it will and exerting its sway on body and society alike, but when it first steps on board, that is at the *learning stage*.

From a theoretical point of view, the rub, the stumbling block with respect to repetition's presumed *autonomy* is always the body and, conversely, its, and not repetition's, *autonomy*. Again, the question: what does incorporating repetition mean? What happens when repetition is integrated in our already existing *habitus*, that is when the repetition device, whatever its nature or historical articulation, encounters the body? A possible answer is that something does not fit; the encounter engenders resistance; there is friction. A word of caution is called for here. If at this point we were to espouse an ideologically skewed view idealistically inclined to interpreting the increasing technicization of the world as moving increasingly in the direction of a general progress, despite encountering stumbling blocks along the way, that is, if we were to think of *habitus* as being capable of attaining an ideal, totally manageable form through small successive adjustments to make up for the occasional mishap along the way, it would mean being blind to the fact that any such enterprise is doomed to failure from the outset, for it is invariably plagued by extrinsic disruptions and an inherent fragility. Something 'goes wrong', has always 'gone wrong', in the acquisition of every *repetition device* by the body. To presume that the body assimilates a repetition technique in a straightforward manner and that the no-technical residue of technicisation will be subsequently reduced is ideologically naïve. The ultimate ideological mistake is perhaps to consider the resistance of the body to be a negligible error, a marginal side effect compared to an instrumental rationality that will ultimately make for the repetition device to effortlessly work in the body, singular and social.

In a nut shell, corporal contrariety is the snag; when a new technique is incorporated into the body, the body resists its domestication. In other words, incorporation of any new mind-set is no smooth and easy process; acquisition of a repetition technique, such as is a *habitus*, induces initial take-up resistance by way of 'natural counter-techniques' within the repetition. As with already acquired techniques, these repulsive techniques are no less repetition driven and their action is to complicate and disrupt the assimilative framework. What exactly holds up assimilation at this crucial intermediate stage? The obstacle to smooth and easy integration is the body; its otherness with respect to the course of events resurfaces at this stage, defiantly counteracting the process's unhindered progress. The body as *Leib*, the lived body, that is, deploys its own 'resistant nature' within the *conatus*. But despite this rejective inclination, it is in any case already in the receptive, acquisitive incorporation mode.

This kind of over-determination is not our problem's fault-line but its logical centre. Succinctly put, the body *is and has* a resistant nature (this tallies with Merleau-Ponty's *we have and are habit*). The theoretical and even political upshot of this inherent corporeal resistance is that the body while constantly adapting is no less always putting up a fight, constantly tending and striving, that is, to be 'disadaptive' no less than it is adaptive. This corporeal contrariety is what makes room for dissent in future action. The bond between body and repetition is not yet a permanent, irreversible given. It is rather a relationship of 'agonistic reciprocity', so much so that there are instances in which it is actually the body, according to its nature, that takes the lead in limiting and restructuring the power of repetition. Each individual body is constantly at work to remould corporal schema. Corporeity, in its relational dimension, which is first and foremost an open and inter-corporeal dimension before being inter-subjective, enriches that same schema with innovative variants, un contemplated by the original scheme itself.

Our contention that focusing attention on already learnt and firmly incorporated techniques and limiting ourselves to a strictly conventional philosophical inquiry can amount to missing the point when learning is the issue should at this point have been soundly established. As much as the given may be relevant and historically decisive, the process of acquisition, of *incorporation* of uncustomary and novel behaviour patterns and/or *habitus* is what we should be looking at more closely if we are to try to understand or even just appreciate the possibility of mind-set change. It is in process and not in *datum* that material and not fictional self-induced variation of repetition patterns may be more comprehensibly observed. And by process we mean precisely that narrow but decisive intermediate 'left' field in which 'old' repetitions are fully foregrounded and performative while 'new' repetitions are as yet competitively 'lurking' in the background, striving for incorporation.

That's not to say that over time learning hasn't altogether received its fair share of intellectual speculation. Some of this speculation is highly pertinent to our discussion of learning new repetitions, that is, of learning new repetition devices,

such as is *habitus*. For reasons of space only a couple of examples can be cursorily considered here. First, let's begin at the beginning, at infancy, at the *infans*, at the stage of the as yet speechless child, the child devoid of cultural influences, the quintessentially open-minded anthropoid, who is nevertheless susceptible and receptive enough for *habitus* – such as linguistic habits, for instance – to take root. The newborn is almost solely corporeity, a primacy that can last up to as many as the first three years. Throughout this time *Leib* begins and continues to learn ceaselessly, caught up and swept along in the ever-flowing learning stream, seizing on every germinal moment, every fleeting experience as they roll by. As we've already seen in the *Nicomachean Ethics*, most importantly the child *learns to repeat*. In elucidating on the concept of *hexis* in which repetition is the key to explaining behaviour habituation, Aristotle shows how a structured behavioural technique *incorporated through repeated exercises* is conducive to the accretion in the individual of *areté*, in accordance with the values of a given social *milieu*. It may be safely presumed that such a process commences to unfold at the earliest stages of childhood development. Viewing Aristotle and what follows in the philosophical speculation on these issues from the standpoint of Merleau-Ponty helps to better appreciate how corporeality is in fact the focus of discussion into the dynamics of mind-set and -frame growth, consolidation, change or dissolution, be it the individual stand-alone body or, even more importantly, the extended, outreaching body of *intercorporeity*. If this be the case in adult life, how far more pivotal, then, is the body in earlier development, in the far less subject-superintended stages of childhood? Body pattern formation and deformation in the behaviour pattern structuring throughout the first three years of infancy, before what Merleau-Ponty in his lectures at the Sorbonne refers to as the 'third year crisis', is of special interest to our discussion here. In particular, one of his insights is especially illuminating. He keenly notes how in the child, «the acquisition of expressive modes always represents a certain crisis, the sudden annexation of an entire expressive universe»⁵⁷. What this amounts to is that while the complex reality to which the infant is submitted has already been manageably schematised and an idiosyncratic behaviour pattern can already be seen to emerge, the schema nevertheless undergoes radical re-formation to make room for new acquisitions. But what goes for the body of the as yet inarticulate *infans* also applies to the body of the politically 'oriented', socially defined, linguistically structured, and whatever else adult – the same, deep-seated, traumatic schema-changing upheaval in ceaseless progress, even though memory of its earliest onset may have completely faded away or awareness of its lingering, underlying presence have been self-censored.

Now that we've seen the primary role of corporeity in the speechless *infans* lets go to the other extreme where repetition's inclusion in the body becomes so deeply entrenched, so ingrained as to warrant the term 'hard-wiring'. This is

⁵⁷ M. Merleau-Ponty, *Les relations avec autrui chez l'enfant*, «Bulletin de Psychologie», tome VIII, 3-6, 236, 1964.

especially the case of the mass production line worker. The alienated, repetitive and machinelike method-engineered gesture of this industrial worker has been the subject of much literature in the last century. The automation of human work and activity in general has today spilled out of the factory over into everyday life. Expanding digital environments, 4.0, the ever faster and more easily accessible multiplatformed Web, Apps for all occasions, and so on are all increasingly encroaching on and cybernating intellectual work, a process that has given rise to a growing intellectual proletariat, the so-called *cognitariat*. In the work milieu learning is learning to do a job. When we speak of learning in this context it is perhaps clearer than in other discourses on the subject that learning is about mastering a technique, which is done through repetition in a skill or procedure. The assembly line worker, for instance, is trained or more precisely drilled to perform a specific task by methodically repeating a technical gesture or a coordinated set of gestures in an orderly and routine fashion without any deviation from given standards. There is strictly no room for body friction in such heavily controlled, limited and constricted behavioural sequences. The space for any behavioural variation, for the divergent-corporeal dimension of the worker's *Leib* to break out from such a strait-jacket is next to nil. 'Improvisation', in the sense Merleau-Ponty uses the term, that is, of human proclivity to vary and adapt one's own schemata by *inventing new ways* of merging the old and the new repetition, is atrophied. Method engineering and 'hard-wiring' of a concatenated sequence of prearranged routine actions constituting a menial task, a skill or a more articulated procedure so as to ensure smooth, snag-free job performance by the human agent requires hard or in any case consistent drilling and entails practically 'automatonising' the body. It is not the only type of knowledge infused in this manner. Education in general is in fact the crux of the matter, the vital and decisive stage of *habitus* and of disciplinary – in Foucault's sense – transfer of work-behavioural contents from the 'system' to the 'body-that-works'. It is in this sense of the structural need to limit any internal resistance that we can appreciate the scope and duties incumbent on a psychotechnician in charge of hiring specialized workers in a factory in Belgium in 1948. Especially illuminating is a note of caution addressed to the recruiter in assessing applicants. The recommendation sheds light on the essential difference between an 'informational logic' and an experience of complexification, typical of every true relationship of formation: «From the moment a worker shows a quick understanding of the procedures, of the delivery that has been entrusted to her to perform a 'test', we call her wake up. [...] In the choice we have to make, we must be wary of workers who succeed too well and too easily in the 'tests': in the long run, they will never get used to too elementary tasks»⁵⁸.

This word of warning to recruiters couldn't be clearer as to how even a minimally critical learning of repetition, amounting to failure to fully hold the *working or productive habitus* in check, risks thwarting the system's scope and

⁵⁸ Quoted in G. Friedmann, *Où va le travail humain?*, Paris 1967, p. 317.

rationale in the 'scientific' selection of the ideal operator, qualified and employable only insofar as an actuating extension of the machine itself. This caveat actually applies well beyond the shop-floor. It is germane to any training programme – whether for selecting manual or intellectual workers – whose promise and scope is to deliver the flawlessly operational, fully self-satisfied and economically achieving trainee in the shortest time possible⁵⁹. Whatever the spin on higher and on-going education, personnel training, refresher courses, upgrading human resources and staff skills and the like, imparting knowledge and/or know-how to the prospective 'wage earner', regardless of rank, seems to still be conceived of and practiced as a one way flow of information from source – in addition to knowledge also the fountainhead of power – to subdued recipient. This being the model prevailing today no less than yesterday, the process of *habitus* formation is still thought of in pedagogically reductive terms, based as it is on the mere, 'no-nonsense' conveyance of information, gauged as successful depending on the recipient's faithful rendering of the conveyed contents, without any alteration. Such an outlook is a far cry from the idea of learning as a truly critical experience conducive to developing one's own personal point of view (the shared dimension of knowledge as a structuring of common experience notwithstanding). To be sure, there's no room in this pedagogically bleak scenario for any lateral thinking. In some form or another, remote and distant teaching and learning have been around for some time now. The recent officially sanctioned and publically supported, pandemic-driven expansion of these educational practices is not without consequence. Despite expert reassurances to the contrary, the reductive model of straight, strictly convergent, drill-based rote learning described above still prevails and has indeed broken new ground. The apparently two way, real-time teacher-learner interaction and exchange made possible by the cyber classroom is illusory as far as the actual direction of information flow and transfer goes. Indeed, on-line enhancement has actually quickened the process of industrialisation of the education sector, like Distance Learning⁶⁰. The tasks required of today's blue or white collar workers may have changed along with the tools and know-how required for performing them, but the agenda is still as much full-scale production process automation as ever, including the human agency as well. As in the past, scope and purpose of much of modern-day on-line teaching and learning is to cost-efficiently upload the learner with instructions

⁵⁹ It is evident, although we cannot dwell on it here, the connection between the acceleration in the *progressions of contemporary technology* and the 'new' forms of control, which highlight, among other things, the constitutive ambiguity of the concept of 'giving a form', in the sense of passivation of the trained subjects, but also to emancipate the subjectivity of those who are authentically trained (and not just merely 'informed'). References could go to the Frankfurt school scholars, such as H. Rosa, *Beschleunigung und Entfremdung. Entwurf einer kritischen Theorie spätmoderner Zeitlichkeit*, Frankfurt 2015, but also to Paul Virilio's work on acceleration. An original vision that integrates Virilio's thought with references to the philosophy of technique, also in Germany, is: U. Fadini, *Velocità e attesa. Tecnica, tempo e controllo in Paul Virilio*, Verona 2020.

⁶⁰ For example DAD: acronym of *didattica a distanza* (distance learning) in Italian.

and turn out fully trained and skilled, specialised no-nonsense ‘technicians’ in as short a time as possible. What is ultimately required of these operators is to be adroit and frictionless cogs in the wheel, even if ‘friendly’ employee incentive and benefit plans and motivation-oriented human resource management helps to disguise the fact. Their duties essentially consist in mastering a procedure so as to be able to smoothly and effortlessly run a programme or implement a protocol; nothing more is asked of them but to execute preordained routines set out sequentially in a list of standardised instructions. Method-engineering thrives and prospers indeed well in the so-called post-industrial age of the twenty first century and a good deal of the groundwork is as ever entrusted to the teaching profession. In fact, with respect to the technique, we could say that it is possessed us more than it is possessed by us.

Some provisional conclusions: learning to learn

Be it then as in the case of the inarticulate infant, of the assembly line worker, of the modern-day operator, repetition technique-based acquisition processes require subjugation of the body. The passivised body is in fact more receptive and ‘machinally’ useable, whereas the aroused and reactive body is obstructive and disruptive, a ‘remainder’ to be trammelled as quickly and securely as possible. Any residual subversive capacity, any dissent that may unwittingly or involuntarily challenge the systematic nature of deep incorporation of repetition automatisms must be speedily dampened. Every critical form will have to be re-addressed in the Program itself (the Program of the global Automatic Machine)⁶¹ to better solve those same schemes or problems, whose form is ‘a not open form but a close form.’

The critique we’ve conducted so far is not intended as end in itself but is merely a premise for the work that lies ahead. It’s important to have a clear albeit summary picture as to where we actually stand to better appreciate our contention that far from referring to a staid, steady and settled mind-set or mental disposition or behavioural pattern, the concept of *habitus* calls forth a significantly more complex and not so sedate scenario. *Habitus* stands at the cross-roads, at the meeting of the turbulent and uncontrollable waters of learning and unlearning, of the *passive reception and incorporation* of a scheme versus its *active acquisition and assimilation*. To a certain extent it may be said to be akin to Gregory Bateson’s⁶² concept of *deutero-learning* (i.e. learning to learn). Left to their own devices, *habits* as second nature, whether inflected in the singular or

⁶¹ The automatism of informational Capitalism, that is the pattern of pseudo-mechanical behaviour induced in the bodies, are at the center of the chapter on time in Stiegler, *La société automatique* (cit., pp. 281-323). Stiegler here thoroughly develops the ‘classic’ reference to *General Intellect* concept, starting from the *Fragment on the machines* of Marx in the *Grundrisse*.

⁶² Cfr. G. Bateson, *Steps to an ecology of mind*, San Francisco 1972; see also, on this topic, I. Pegreffi, *Filosofia dell’automatismo*, cit.

the social, can be divergent and disruptive in their instantiation, proving to be far less routinary than what might be expected. Bearing as much in mind, a path can be traced for the future, down which to pursue one of the major issues raised in the present discussion. *Habitus* deserves more than a second look, as it is around this concept that essential questions as to what we mean by learning and hence education in general are and will played out, theoretically and in practice. As we have seen, when it comes to theorising about *habitus* and its practical policy fallout, the state of the art is still today solidly and stably founded on the idea of learning as blinkered assimilation of repetition techniques aimed at maximising behavioural automatisms. Cognizant that this is the *status quo*, we can move on to a more fruitful and meaningful critique.

Foremost on the agenda is the need to challenge, at every turn, in whatever context and for whatever practice, be it in reference to workplace conditions and organisation, to production processes, and even to so-called leisure-time activities, the naive blanket idea that *habitus* amounts to assimilating repetition and that the measure of successful assimilation is the habit-forming straitjacket's tightness. As we have seen, any repetition device is forever susceptible to change upon coming into contact and interacting with the organic. Unless artfully or even forcefully subdued, the body inherently counters, as Merleau-Ponty points out, uploading and effortlessly assimilating and automatising 'as is' any new inputted body scheme, automatism, or technique. The possibility of unlearning, of de-automating learning is never wholly forsaken; it is always an option and indeed, as Olivier Houdé cogently argues in his recent book *Apprendre à résister*, it's never too late to «learn to resist»⁶³. Neuroscientists claim to have even found and recorded physiological variations at the synaptic level correlating with new activations in the neuronal network. This so-called «cognitive instant»⁶⁴ is no less constitutively corporeal, tactile and polysensory. What's important about it for our purposes is that it allows us to identify a somatopsychic space, a dynamic field in which incumbent, incorporated *habitus* mingles and blends in with new, still pliable, wannabe *habitus*. Here then is an opening for reevaluating critical learning. Houdé's broad approach takes into account theories and findings from many fields, including neuroscience, pedagogy, sociology and philosophy. Whatever the angle, Houdé finds that the neuronal networks engendered in learning any technique is a process invariably associated with a 'background noise', which he calls «cognitive resistance»⁶⁵. Not only does this 'noise' surface, becoming behaviourally patent, but it also has physical ramifications, deeply embodied as it is in the folds of our singular but above all cooperative and social corporeity. Most importantly, according to Houdé, is the fact that this resistance is the result of a positive process of «inhibition»⁶⁶ in the form of a repulsive

⁶³ O. Houdé, *Apprendre à résister*, Paris 2017.

⁶⁴ *Ivi*, p. 5.

⁶⁵ *Ivi*, p. 9.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

counter-movement with respect to «one's own impulsive, too rapid responses»⁶⁷. What's more, this counteractive rather than reactive, cogitative rather than 'pavlovianly' automatic restraining process is concomitant to learning; indeed it is part and parcel of the learning process itself. From the cortex through the sensory organs to the motor plexuses, the body is fully caught up in the acquisition of any new pattern, but to the learning process its resistance is of far greater consequence than its submission.

Is there still room for dissent once an automatism is up and running in the fully deployed *habitus*? Is there any option left open, any latitude for a new twist, any chance of breaking the routine once a behavioural and even 'life' regulating and patterning technique is in place and successfully working 'under cover', unbeknown, that is, the interested party? Positively yes, Houdé's extensive study allows us to say. Our corporeality always harbours deep-seated layers of resistance, concrete psycho-physical resources to draw on, to feed a form of criticism of the self same action we are at any moment performing in compliance with the acquired and incorporated technique. And that goes for any action in whatever context, be at work, at leisure, imaginative, erotic, educational, artistic action, individual or social.

The scientific literature focuses on narrower topics, such as psychomotor aspects and induced neuro-cerebral plasticity⁶⁸, rather than the wider, more philosophical issues that interest us here. They are nonetheless germane to our discussion as they provide proof of the body's prominent role in learning/dislearning processes and point to the possibility of not only countering and turning around the currently dominant, fast-yielding, 'method-engineering' approach to educational practice but also of prioritising our lives differently and more beneficially. Acknowledgement of corporeality's key role can radically change our outlook on education. Instead of viewing, for instance, the body's inherent resistance to acquiring let alone incorporate executive instruction- and routine-laden techniques as a hindrance to learning, this counteractive proclivity could be deployed for a new, more critical *style of learning*. Instead of practicing an asymmetrical, one-sided teacher-to-learner conveyance of knowledge and know-how through technical repetition, with all the attendant performance failures, misunderstandings, errors, and the like, better and more person-centred learning might be achievable through a reciprocated and interactive approach.

Opening up to and drawing on the plastically resourceful passivity of entire forgotten layers of our corporeity is also conducive to enhanced inter-corporeity, a functionally facilitating prerequisite for acquiring the repetition inherent in *habitus* in a less grindingly drill-instilling, routinized way. The time and motion paradigm was the apex of the industrial revolution 1.0, but method engineering,

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ On the issue of learning and neuroplasticity, see also the 'classic' N. Carr, *The Swallows. What the Internet is doing to our brains*, New York 2010, as well as recent critical studies like Ippolita, *Anime elettriche. Riti e miti social*, Milano 2016 or T. Berns, A. Rouvroy, *Gouvernementalité algorithmique et perspective d'émancipation*, «Réseaux», n. 177, 20, 2013, pp. 163-196.

as we have tried to argue here, is still very much alive and kicking in one form or another today, in our post-industrial or industry 4.0 era, however one chooses to call it. This paradigm has spilled over from the factory workshop to service industries and far beyond, into our everyday lives even; it has to change if we are to relate more 'wholesomely' to repetition. In theory and practice the line worth going down envisages a more complex, slower, less flustering and blustering, more sedate approach to learning, without the fetish of immediate success, and where the learning environment is alive, co-operative, open to history and exchange, not unlike the kind of environment that one may come across in an artisan's workshop. This 'arts-and-crafts-like' approach is what Richard Sennett endorses, for example, in his criticism of the Promethean dimension of technical repetition devices in *The craftsman*⁶⁹.

More than ever today, then, the agenda reads: '*Craftsmanship within Learning*'. This means lacing learning *habitus* with a dose of *craft*. Dexterity and proficiency in expediting acquired technical skills, be they manual or cognitive, are already standard fare. But it is not enough to have learnt how to deliver the goods quickly and efficiently. Learning technique for expeditiously executing a task needs to be integrated with a good measure of *artistry in solving* new problems starting from the existing framework. Crafting means both ability in re-forming the existing mind-set and 'ruse' in inventing new ways of actively and passively relating to our *habitus*. According to Sennett, these relations need to be more cooperative and gregarious. Despite all the hype and spin around social media, the challenge confronting our advanced post-industrial societies is inconspicuously creeping de-socialization. If we are to attempt to finally subvert the disempowering, asymmetrical relationship inherent in the currently dominant digital frame of cultural reference with its dire and drastic 0-1, input-output linearity; if we are to overcome having taken to extremes the time-and-motion paradigm by greatly shortening the stimulus-to-response time interval based on a utilitarian calculus enabled by digital technology; if we are to try to counter the gross trivialization of learning reduced to mere training through drilling or the binarized impoverishment of experience, Sennett suggests that we need to change our habits or *habitus*, or rather our way of forming them, thinking of how they may be sustained in a communal, highly stimulating, interactional environment of cognitive companionship and mutual engagement and exploration.

It's at that mute and subdued, inconspicuous stage of *learning new automatisms within habitus* that a different attitude to learning may be fostered. It entails a material change in outlook away from the idea of learning as training, as acquisition of techniques in as schematically a mode and short a time as possible. It calls for de-prioritizing productivity according to monetarily quantifiable outcomes and efficiency metrics. It means thinking that learning can also be a slow, holistic process conducive to a personal experience of change.

⁶⁹ See R. Sennett, *The Craftsman*, New York 2008.

It is necessary to put oneself in a different frame of mind right from the start, setting aside ideas such as that learning means becoming skilled and proficient in executing a task, optimising performance, and minimising the time taken to complete it. It means appreciating knowledge for its own sake and intrinsic value and making room for incorporating new knowledge, taking necessary time out to do so. It requires reconsidering knowledge accrual as a streaming process of personal development, without losing sight of the fact that resistance in the *habitus* is potentially critical leverage and acuity at work. In short, it means having a less grossly functional and more enrichingly informational, a less crudely instructional and more empoweringly educational, a less utilitarian and more humanitarian, a less acquisitive and more inquisitive approach to knowledge accrument and *habitus* formation.

Igor Pelgreffi
Università degli Studi di Verona
✉ igor.pelgreffi@univr.it